

THE FEATURES OF ARTIFICIAL BILINGUALISM FORMATION IN STUDENTS

Mamadiyarova Dilfuza Umirzakovna

Doctor of Philosophy in Psychology, Associate Professor of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology of the Samarkand State Medical University

Radjabboev Asror Alisherovich

Urgench State University

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Abstract: Artificial bilingualism refers to the structured, intentional process of teaching a second language within an educational setting, as opposed to natural bilingualism, which occurs in a multilingual environment. This educational practice is gaining importance in today's globalized world, where language skills offer significant cognitive, academic, and cultural benefits to students. The formation of artificial bilingualism is typically achieved through pedagogical methods like immersion programs, Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), and scaffolded language progression. These approaches aim to simulate the natural acquisition of a second language, providing students with both language proficiency and enhanced cognitive abilities such as better memory, problem-solving, and multitasking skills.

Key challenges in developing artificial bilingualism include limited language exposure outside the classroom, maintaining student motivation, and adapting methods to different age groups. Despite these challenges, artificial bilingualism fosters cultural awareness, improves academic outcomes, and offers significant career advantages. Successful bilingual education depends on the continuous adaptation of teaching strategies, as well as providing ample language input through teacher-student interaction, multimedia resources, and peer communication.

Keywords: artificial bilingualism, multimedia resources, communication.

Introduction

Bilingualism, or the ability to communicate effectively in two languages, has become increasingly important in today's globalized world. As the demand for multilingual professionals rises, educational systems are focusing on fostering bilingualism in students. While natural bilingualism occurs when a person grows up in an environment where two languages are spoken, **artificial bilingualism** refers to the structured teaching of a second language in an educational setting. The formation of artificial bilingualism in students presents unique challenges and benefits, involving deliberate teaching strategies and methods aimed at equipping learners with proficiency in a second language.

Defining Artificial Bilingualism

Artificial bilingualism involves the **intentional** teaching of a second language through formal education. Unlike natural bilingualism, where individuals acquire two languages

simultaneously in their everyday environment, artificial bilingualism is shaped by structured pedagogical approaches. This typically occurs in **monolingual societies** where students are introduced to a second language at school. The process involves curriculum design, language exposure, and cognitive adjustments that aim to emulate the natural process of bilingual language acquisition.

Key Features of Artificial Bilingualism Formation

- 1. Pedagogical Approaches and Methods** The success of artificial bilingualism relies heavily on the methods and approaches used by educators. Some of the most common approaches include:
 - **Immersion programs:** In immersion education, the second language is not just taught as a subject but is used as the medium of instruction for other subjects, such as science or history. This full-time exposure helps students develop proficiency in the second language faster by engaging with it in various academic contexts.
 - **Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL):** This method combines teaching subject content through the medium of a foreign language. The dual-focus nature of CLIL ensures that students improve their language skills while simultaneously mastering academic content.
 - **Scaffolding and gradual progression:** In many programs, language learning progresses in stages, from basic vocabulary and grammar to more complex structures. This phased approach is essential for students to build confidence and fluency in the second language.
- 2. Cognitive Development** Artificial bilingualism involves significant cognitive development. The brain's capacity to manage two languages improves certain cognitive skills, such as:
 - **Executive function:** Students exposed to two languages in educational contexts develop stronger attention control, problem-solving, and multitasking abilities. This is because they frequently need to switch between languages, fostering cognitive flexibility.
 - **Memory:** Learning a second language helps improve **working memory**, as students must retain and use vocabulary and grammar rules across two language systems.
 - **Metalinguistic awareness:** Artificial bilingualism helps learners develop an understanding of how languages work, enhancing their ability to analyze language structures, which can also boost literacy in their first language.
- 3. Language Input and Exposure** One of the most crucial aspects of developing artificial bilingualism is providing sufficient **language input**. Unlike natural bilinguals, who are exposed to both languages at home or in society, artificial bilinguals rely on structured educational environments for language exposure. Therefore, language input must be consistent and rich to ensure proficiency. This can be achieved through:
 - **Multimedia and technology:** Incorporating digital resources such as language learning apps, videos, and interactive platforms can offer students more frequent and varied exposure to the second language.
 - **Teacher-student interaction:** Teachers must ensure that they consistently use the second language in their interactions with students to provide real-time language practice.
 - **Peer interaction:** Encouraging communication in the second language between students helps reinforce learning and builds confidence.
- 4. Challenges in Artificial Bilingualism** The formation of artificial bilingualism is not without its challenges. Some of the key obstacles include:

- **Limited exposure:** In many monolingual societies, students may only interact with the second language during school hours, limiting their opportunities to practice outside the classroom. Without sufficient exposure, fluency development can be hindered.
 - **Motivation:** Maintaining high levels of motivation can be difficult, particularly when students are not exposed to the second language in their everyday lives. Artificial bilingualism programs must incorporate motivational strategies, such as gamification, to keep students engaged.
 - **Age factor:** Research indicates that younger learners are more adept at acquiring a second language due to the brain's plasticity. Older students may face more significant challenges when learning a new language, making early introduction to bilingualism a key factor in success.
5. **Cultural Integration** Alongside language learning, the development of artificial bilingualism often includes an introduction to the culture associated with the language being learned. This cultural immersion can enhance students' appreciation and understanding of the second language. Some schools include **cultural components** in their curriculum, such as celebrating foreign holidays or teaching history and literature in the second language, to enrich the learning experience.

Benefits of Artificial Bilingualism

Despite the challenges, the benefits of artificial bilingualism are substantial:

- **Enhanced cognitive abilities:** As mentioned, bilinguals often outperform monolinguals in tasks requiring cognitive flexibility, memory, and problem-solving.
- **Academic success:** Bilingualism has been shown to improve academic performance, especially in areas like mathematics, where problem-solving and critical thinking are vital.
- **Cultural awareness:** Bilingual students tend to be more open to different cultures and perspectives, a trait that is increasingly valuable in the globalized workforce.
- **Career advantages:** Proficiency in more than one language provides students with competitive advantages in the job market, as employers increasingly seek candidates who can communicate across languages.

Conclusion

The formation of artificial bilingualism in students requires careful planning, structured teaching methods, and consistent exposure to the second language. By utilizing pedagogical approaches like immersion and CLIL, educators can foster a learning environment that mimics natural bilingual acquisition. Despite the challenges of limited exposure and motivation, the cognitive, academic, and cultural benefits make artificial bilingualism a highly valuable asset for students in an interconnected world. To maximize the impact, programs must adapt to the needs of learners and offer varied opportunities for language practice, ensuring long-term success in bilingual proficiency.

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